

Original article

Role of Ultrasound in Diagnosis of Carpel Tunnel Syndrome

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ABSTRACT

Keywords:

Carpal Tunnel Syndrome (CTS)
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Carpel tunnel syndrome (CTS) is the most common mononeuropathy with a significant morbidity and good treatment outcome. Several studies from around the world reported that the high-resolution ultrasound (US) becomes the first line noninvasive technique in diagnosis of CTS by measurement of the cross-sectional area (CSA) of the median nerve (MN) proximal to the site of entrapment and with variable cut-off value = 9-11 mm². According to various studies, it is both sensitive (82% - 89%) and specific (83% - 97%) for the diagnosis of CTS. in comparison with nerve conduction studies (NCS). Nerve swelling showed the highest accuracy (91%) among gray-scale ultrasound. The aims of this study were to determine the CSA of the MN among Libyan population and to confirm the accuracy of high-resolution ultrasound in diagnosis of the CTS in comparison with NCS. A case-control study was performed during 2018 at Radiology Department - AL-Hawari General Hospital by Radiologist using high-resolution ultrasound. The number of patients was 57 and the number of wrists studied of these patients was seventy wrists presented with unilateral or bilateral symptoms of CTS examined by US and their NCS were performed. A control group of 200 wrists of 100 healthy subjects were included to determine the median nerve CSA cut-off in the Libyan population. The cut-off point for Median nerve CSA in the Libyan patients = <9 mm² was considered in-patient with CTS. CTS were bilateral in 13 cases and unilateral in 44 cases. Ultrasound examination for the diagnosis of CTS is painless, cost effective, tolerable to patients comparing to the NCS and measurement of the median nerve cross-sectional area is both sensitive and specific for such purpose. It is recommended that the high-resolution ultrasound examination should be used as a first line test for the diagnosis of CTS.

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INTRODUCTION

Carpal Tunnel Syndrome is the symptomatic presentation of median nerve entrapment at the wrist and the most common mononeuropathy [1]. The prevalence of CTS in the general population ranges from 2.7% to 5.8%. The most commonly seen cases are: aged over 40 years and 65% to 75% of patients are females, with a female/male ratio ranging from 3:1 to 10:1 [1,2]. Variability in prevalence data could be due to variations in occupational and industrial work exposure. A majority of patients attribute their CTS to work exposure. It causes burden for work related morbidity; 90% have a good treatment outcome and are able to return from work, but 10% are permanently disabled [1,2]. Carpal tunnel syndrome is the most prevalent chronic peripheral nerve compression syndrome. It is a suite of symptoms caused by localized median nerve

compression at the wrist; its incidence is 99 per 100,000 individuals [3]. This syndrome may result from transient ischemic episodes linked to microvascular disorders, or from median nerve compression because of a reduction in tunnel volume or an increase in the volume of tunnel contents [4]. Changes in the wrist position or application of external forces can lead to increased pressure resulting in median nerve entrapment and injury. Normal pressure in the Carpal tunnel ranges from 2 - 10 mmHg. Anomalous contents within the canal and the position of its internal structures can decrease the available canal space. These anomalous contents represented by edema, inflammation, hemorrhage deposits of pathologic substances such as calcium uric, and/or conditions of amyloidosis. The most common systemic causes are diabetes mellitus, rheumatoid

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arthritis, hypothyroidism, acromegaly and other collagen diseases. CTS can also appear during pregnancy or from hormonal alteration pathologies or secondary to a traumatic wrist Accident or fracture [4,5]. When the cause of CTS is not clear, it is defined as idiopathic. These forms are the most frequently occurring. CTS more frequently occur in the subject's dominant hand, which also happens to be the hand that works the most. Various wrist flexion and extension movements provoke an increase in pressure with repetitive phases of median nerve compression. It has been demonstrated that internal canal pressure varies with the variation of wrist position. When the nerve is under tension it bends and rests against the canal's borders thus provoking this type of compression phenomenon [4].

More recently, high frequency US, magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) have been able to demonstrate median nerve compression long with the detection of space-occupying lesions within the carpal tunnel and flexor tendon pathology. Sliding of the median nerve during dynamic studies with flexion of the fingers can also be evaluated. Both, MRI and US can also be employed in the diagnosis of post-operative conditions and surgical complications [4].

The high frequency US becomes more recognizable as the first line noninvasive diagnostic technique [1]. It traces the circumference of the median nerve proximal to the site of entrapment and the measurement of the CSA has a variable cut-off ranging from 9-11 mm² according to several studies [6-14]. This variability is affected by group ethnicity [15]. US measurement of CSA is both sensitive (sensitivity 82% - 89%) and specific (76% - 97%) for diagnosis of CTS [7,11,13]. In comparison with nerve conduction studies, nerve swelling showed the highest accuracy (91%) among gray-scale sonography criteria [14,16].

Roll et al. (2011) reported that a moderate to strong correlations were noted between electro-diagnostic testing results and sonographic measurements of the CSA at the pisiform, retinaculum bowing, and both the ratio and change of the CSA between the forearm and pisiform, sensitivity was high (80.4%-82.4%). The cutoff value for MN CSA was 9 mm² in mild cases of CTS reaching up to 32 mm² in severe cases [17].

S. Billakota, L.D. Hobson-Webb (2017) found out that the wrist to forearm ratio (WFR) of CSA (wrist CSA/forearm CSA) was calculated. CSA > 9 mm² and WFR >1.4 were used as cut-off values [10].

Electrodiagnostic studies consist of a combination of nerve conduction studies (NCS) both (motor & sensory) and needle electromyography (EMG) provides information about the muscle innervated by the nerve. [2] The Diagnostic criteria for CTS, evidence of sensory nerve fiber compression; Absent or delayed motor nerve SAP (>3.4 m/s), Increased median-to-ulnar latency, difference of the fourth finger SAP (0.5 m/s), evidence of motor nerve fiber compression, increased distal motor latency (>4.2 ms), and denervation signs in the abductor pollicis brevis muscle [4].

METHODS

Seventy wrists of 57 patients with unilateral or bilateral symptoms of carpal tunnel syndrome, referred to radiology department of AL-Hawari General Hospital from the neurosurgery and, orthopedic clinics, and other polyclinic in Benghazi city were included in this study between January and December 2018. Verbal consents were obtained from all patients. The carpal tunnel syndrome was bilateral in 13 cases and unilateral in 44 cases. All patients had characteristic clinical symptoms of CTS e.g., nocturnal paresthesia in the hand, numbness and tingling hand and wrist paresthesia during activities or pain and their electrodiagnostic tests were performed.

Patients with a history of previous wrist surgery or fracture, conditions associated with neuropathy (e.g., hypothyroidism, diabetes mellitus, chronic renal failure, rheumatoid arthritis and pregnancy) and those with degenerative articular pathologies such as arthritis of the trapeziometacarpal joint and scaphoid pseudoarthrosis or clinical findings of any other neuropathies (e.g., cervical radiculopathy) were excluded.

The US equipment used (Philips), with 5 - 12 MHz linear transducer. The depth was adjusted between 25 and 30 mm. the probe was putted gently with no pressure over a thin layer of gel. The study is performed in the transverse and longitudinal scan planes. The MN cross sectional area (CSA) was measured by manual continuous tracing technique at the level of pisiform bone; a widely accepted cutoff cross-sectional area for CTS with the highest sensitivity and specificity is 10 mm², measured at the carpal tunnel inlet or pisiform. A control group of 200 wrists of 100 patients were examined by the same sequence.

The patients should be sitting in a couch with extended arms, forearms were in supination position, and wrists were neutral with fingers semi-extended using the palmer surface of the wrist resting over a bellow.

Ultrasound allows the visualization of all the soft tissue components of carpal tunnel (tendons, median nerve, and transverse carpal ligament) Normal tendons are hyperechoic and the normal median nerve will have an internal fascicular pattern, characterized as a "honeycomb" appearance each nerve fascicles will be hypoechoic and outlined by hyperechoic connective tissue.

Color and power Doppler ultrasound can detect the presence of intraneural vascularity, which would indicate the presence of inflammatory changes within the nerve. Studies have shown the sensitivity and specificity to be as high as 83% and 89% respectively, also observed restricted median nerve mobility in CTS, Real-time ultrasound allows for dynamic evaluation during passive flexion and extension of the digits. This is thought to be due to fibrosis or adherence of the median nerve to the retinaculum. Flexor retinacular bowing and median nerve flattening ratios are measured in a similar fashion as MRI.

Standardized nerve conduction studies were performed by one of several neurologists, using surface electrodes.

The antidromic sensory median nerve conduction velocity, the distal motor latency, and the median motor compound muscle action potential were determined. Age-dependent normal values were 41–53m/sec for sensory conduction velocity, and 3.9–4.1 m/sec for distal motor latency, and 5 mV for muscle action potential. There is no universally accepted diagnostic reference standard for CTS.

RESULTS

Fifty-seven patients (70 wrists) were included in this study; sixty-two females (87.2%) and eight males (12.8%), the mean ± SD of their age was 39.19 ± 9.60, ranging between (22-65years old); and 100 control volunteers (200 wrists) 149 were female (74.5%) and 51 were male (24.5 %), their age ranged (18-75) years old with mean age ± SD (35.12± 11.30) as shown by figure (1) and table (1, 2).

Fig.1. Comparison between the control and study groups according to the gender.

Table 1. Comparison between the two groups of the study according to their age

Case of CTS group (70) Age in years		Control group (200) Age in years	
Mean	39.19	Mean	35.12
Std. Deviation	9.60	Std. Deviation	11.30
Minimum	22	Minimum	18
Maximum	65	Maximum	75

Table 2. Distribution of the CTS patient by age and gender group

Age group (in years)	Gender		Total
	Female	Male	
20-30	8(15.4%)	3(6%)	11(19.2%)
31-40	18(34.6%)	1(2%)	19(33.3%)
41-50	1(2%)	20(38.5%)	21(35%)
> 50	6(11.5%)	0(0%)	6(10.5%)
Total	52(100%)	5 (100%)	57(100%)

Fifty wrists diagnosed by CTS in the right hand (71.4%) and twenty wrists in left hand (28.6%). Symptoms were bilateral in thirteen patients (22.8%), left in seven patients and right in thirty-seven patients, as shown by figure (2).

Fig. 2. The laterality of the CTS that is more in the right than left hand

The mean ± (SD) cross-sectional area was 0.07±(0.009) cm² in wrists without CTS and 0.12±(0.027) cm² in wrists with CTS. The mean ± (SD); thickness of the median nerve was 4.3±(1.047) mm in control group and 5.2± (1.466) mm in case group. There is a statistically significant difference between the CSA and thickness of the median nerve of the symptomatic is more compared to the asymptomatic groups.

There is no significant difference between the two groups regarding the AP diameter of the median nerve as the mean ± (SD) of the AP diameter was 2.04 ± (0.397) mm in wrists without and 2.08± (0.474) mm in wrists with CTS.

Table 3. Comparison between the two groups of the study according to the cross-sectional area thickness and AP diameter

The study Group	Cross-section area of the median nerve(cm ²)	Thickness of the median nerve (mm)	AP diameter of the median nerve (mm)
	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD	Mean ± SD
Control	0.07 ± 0.009	4 ± 1.047	2 ± 0.474
Case	0.12 ± 0.027	5 ± 1.466	2 ± 0.397

Correlation between Median Nerve Cross-Sectional Area and the Severity of CTS

The mean ± SD of the CSA was 0.12± (0.027) cm² (range, 0.10-0.14cm²) in mild CTS, (range0.12-0.15cm²) in moderate, and (range, 0.16-0.2) in severe CTS. We detected a significant correlation between MN CSA and the severity of CTS (p< 0.05by 95% CI analysis of variance)

The seventy wrists classified as follow: fifty-two cases as mild (73 %), nine as moderate (13.5 %), and nine as severe CTS (13.5 %) according to the NCS, which used as a golden standard for the CTS diagnosis, as figure (6) reveals.

Fig. 3. Box plot reveals the relationship between the severity of CTS and the cross-sectional area

DISCUSSION

The diagnosis of CTS is based mainly on the patient's history and the clinical findings. The value of provocative physical tests, such as Tinel's or Phalen's tests for CTS is controversial and results are often of doubtful clinical significance. Confirmation of CTS is usually based on nerve conduction studies parameters are abnormal only if there is significant demyelination of axonal loss in the large myelinated fibers [10].

NCS have been considered the "gold standard" in its diagnosis. However, false negative rates for nerve conduction studies have been seen with a range of 16%–34%. Furthermore, it is uncomfortable to the patients and does not give information on the anatomy of the median nerve and its surrounding structures [4]. Recently, ultrasonography has emerged as a painless and cost-efficient diagnostic alternative to NCS [4]. Buchberger et al. were the first to quantify changes in carpal tunnel syndrome using sonography [6]. Their findings confirmed those of earlier MRI studies. Thus, criteria for MRI and sonography have become similar. Further advantages of sonography include its noninvasive, fast, convenient handling, and performance capacity, suggesting its potential role as an inexpensive and quick guide for therapeutic intervention [2]. The results of our study confirm the findings of previous research indicating the CSA of the median nerve at the pisiform as strongly correlated with NCS [4].

We found that CSA with a cut-off value $> 9 \text{ mm}^2$ is diagnostic CTS with sensitivity and specificity of 100% which is matched with Billakota et al who found CSA $> 9 \text{ mm}^2$ [10]. Regarding the thickness of the median nerve a cut off value of 6.5 mm is highly suggestive of the presence of CTS with sensitivity and specificity of 80%, 100% respectively. However, no role for MN AP diameter in the diagnosis of CTS, according to the severity of the disease we found a significant correlation between the increase of the CSA and the CTS severity: CSA ranging between (10-12 mm^2) considering mild, (13-15 mm^2) classified as a moderate and ($> 15 \text{ mm}^2$) severe degree; which is matched with Duncan et al (1999) who found that the most predictive measurement in CTS patients compared with controls is quantitative assessment of the median nerve CSA that being highly predictive of CTS [7].

The study confirmed that median nerve cross-sectional area measurement correlates well with the presence of CTS when the cut-off value was $> 9 \text{ cm}^2$ with sensitivity 82%; and specificity, 97%. Mourad et al in (2018) also revealed that the cut-off value for MNA was 9 mm^2 in mild cases of CTS, reaching up to 32 mm^2 in severe cases [9]. This is matched with Billakota et al who postulated that CSA $> 9 \text{ mm}^2$ was considered diagnostic of CTS [10]. Wong et al provided a diagnostic sensitivity of 89 % and a specificity of 83% [23]. Sonographic measurement of the median nerve CSA is both sensitive and specific for the diagnosis of CTS with a cut-off value $> 0.098 \text{ cm}^2$ at the tunnel inlet [23]. Abdel Ghaffar M.K. et al. (2012) defined median nerve swelling, if CSA was 11 mm^2 [8]. In comparison with NCS, median nerve swelling showed the highest accuracy (89%) among the gray scale sonographic criteria [8]. Similarly, Mallouhi et al. confirmed the CTS in 172 wrists diagnosed by NCS and showed a median nerve CSA of at least 0.11 cm^2 which was calculated as a definition of median nerve swelling [14]. In comparison with nerve conduction studies, nerve swelling showed the highest accuracy (91%) among gray-scale sonography criteria [14]. Ziswiler et al concluded that a cutoff 10 mm^2 of the median nerve CSA with 82% of sensitivity and 76% specificity and highly recommended the Sonography assessment of the median nerve in patient with CTS. [12]. Billakota S et al CSA $> 9 \text{ mm}^2$ and WFR > 1.4 were used as cut-off values for the diagnosis of CTS [9].

CONCLUSION

Ultrasound examination for the diagnosis of carpal tunnel syndrome is painless, cost effective, tolerable to patients comparing to the NCS and measurement of the median nerve cross-sectional area is both sensitive and specific for such purpose.

Recommendation

We recommend the usage of the ultrasound examination as a first line test for the diagnosis of CTS.

Conflict of interests

There are no conflicts of interest regarding the publication of this paper.

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